

Rate Measurements of Complex Formation of Iron(III) with β -Diketones in 4-Methyl-2-pentanone by Solvent Extraction Method

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The rate of solvent extraction of iron(III) in aqueous perchlorate solutions with three β -diketones (HA), 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione, 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluoro-1,3-butanedione, and 1,1,1-trifluoro-2,4-pentanedione, into 4-methyl-2-pentanone has been determined and the reaction mechanism in each system was considered. From the results, two reaction routes were concluded, (i) Fe^{3+} formed complexes in the aqueous phase and the complexes thus formed were extracted and (ii) Fe^{3+} was first extracted into the organic phase as ion-pairs with perchlorate ions and then underwent complex formation in that phase. From the dependence of the rate on the components, the controlling reaction was concluded in the both routes to be the formation of the first complex. The rate of reactions in route (i) was calculated from the rate constants in literature, and by subtracting this from the experimental data, the rate of reaction in route (ii) was obtained. The value of rate constants for the complex formation of iron(III) in 4-methyl-2-pentanone were then calculated.

IN the course of a systematic study on the kinetics of solvent extraction of metal ions with chelating extractants, it has been observed that the rate of solvent extraction of some metal ions with β -diketones is higher when the diluent was a polar solvent, such as 4-methyl-2-pentanone than when it was a non-polar one, such as carbon tetrachloride, and this was especially marked when the perchlorate concentration in the aqueous phase was high¹⁻³. This difference in the rate of extraction with different diluent was explained in terms that the metal ions and/or charged metal complexes formed in the aqueous phase were extracted as ion-pairs with perchlorate ions in the aqueous phase and then they underwent further complex formation in the organic phase; such a second reaction route increased the whole rate of extraction. However, the details of the rate of complex formation in such organic solvents are not very much known. The present paper describes a kinetic study of solvent extraction of iron(III) with three β -diketones into 4-methyl-2-pentanone (isobutyl methyl ketone) in order to learn more about the reaction mechanism in solvent extraction systems in which complex formation takes place in the organic phase.

Experimental

All the reagents were reagent grade. Pure iron metal was dissolved in nitric acid and then iron(III) hydroxide was precipitated by ammonia water. The precipitates were separated and washed several times with water and aqueous sodium perchlorate solution. Then they were dissolved in perchloric acid to prepare the stock solution.

β -Diketone was supplied from Dojindo Co., Kumamoto (Hbfa, Htfa), Tokyo Kasei Co., Tokyo (Hbza). The benzoylacetone (Hbza; 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione) and benzoyltrifluoroacetone (Hbfa; 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluoro-1,3-butanedione) were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, but trifluoroacetylacetone (Htfa; 1,1,1-trifluoro-2,4-pentanedione) was used without further purification. 4-Methyl-2-pentanone was washed with perchloric acid (0.5 mol dm⁻³), water and aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.5 mol dm⁻³) and then several times with water. Sodium perchlorate was recrystallised three times from water. A weighed amount of one of the β -diketones was dissolved in 4-methyl-2-pentanone and stored overnight before the use.

All the procedures were carried out in a thermostated room at 298 K. Stopped glass tubes (capacity 20 cm³) were used for agitation of the two liquid phases. A portion of an aqueous perchlorate solution, (Na, H)ClO₄ (4 mol dm⁻³) containing iron(III) (1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) was placed in a tube and the same volume of 4-methyl-2-pentanone containing a β -diketone was added. The two phases were agitated so vigorously that no increase in the rate of extraction was found by an increase in the agitation speed. After a certain time, the two phases were centrifuged off. The extracted iron(III) was stripped from the organic phase by nitric acid (4 mol dm⁻³). Iron(III) in the washed solution and that extracted and remained in the aqueous phase was determined by atomic absorption method. The hydrogen-ion concentration in the aqueous phase (the stoichiometric units) was determined potentiometrically before and after the two phase agitation

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by using a series of standard solutions. The acid concentration in these standard solutions was determined by titration with standard aqueous sodium hydroxide solutions.

Statistical :

In the present paper, a β -diketone is denoted by HA. Any chemical species in the organic phase is denoted by a subscript 'org' and those in the aqueous phase by lack of any subscript.

Since the two-phase agitation was made so vigorously, effect of any interfacial reaction on the rate will be regarded negligible in the present study.

As was pointed out in a previous paper⁴, when the complex formation in the aqueous phase controls the whole process, the rate of extraction is not always identical with the rate of complex formation. However, it was also pointed out that the difference between the rate of complex formation and of solvent extraction should be negligible when the extraction at equilibrium is quantitative as in the present study. The rate of extraction may generally be written as

$$V = -d[\text{Fe}^{3+}]/dt = \sum k_{(b)}[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HA}]^a[\text{H}^+]^b \quad (1)$$

From this, the following equation is introduced,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \sum k_{(b)}[\text{HA}]^a[\text{H}^+]^b \quad (2)$$

and the value of k_{obs} under certain concentration of [HA] and $[\text{H}^+]$ can be determined from the slope of $\log[\text{Fe}^{3+}]$ against time⁵.

Results and Discussion

It was reported in previous papers that the rate of solvent extraction of iron(III) in aqueous perchlorate solutions (4 mol dm^{-3}) with 2-thenyl-trifluoroacetone (Htta) is higher when the diluent was 4-methyl-2-pentanone than when it was carbon tetrachloride^{2,3} and having similar results with acetylacetone when the metal ion was chromium(III)^{5,6}.

In the present study, this higher rate of solvent extraction into the polar solvent was also found with the β -diketones studied. For example, when the initial extractant concentration in the organic phase was 0.1 mol dm^{-3} and initial acid concentration in the aqueous phase was 0.1 mol dm^{-3} , the rate of extraction of iron(III) into 4-methyl-2-pentanone was approximately 11 times, and 17 times higher than that into carbon tetrachloride when the β -diketone was Hbza and Hbfa. However when it was Htfa, the rate of extraction into 4-methyl-2-pentanone was somewhat lower (about 0.75 times) than into carbon tetrachloride. This was found to be due to an apparent effect; when the diluent is carbon tetrachloride and the reagent is Htfa, about 30% of it in the system is present in the aqueous phase and this fraction of the reagent undergoes complex formation, but when the reagent is one of the other two bulky β -diketones, only about 0.2% of them in the system is present in the aqueous phase.

Since the complex formation takes place only in the aqueous phase when the diluent is non-polar, the rate of solvent extraction is much lower with one of the latter two if the total amount of the reagent in the system is the same. On the other hand, when the diluent is 4-methyl-2-pentanone, the complex formation takes place in both the phases. Although the rate of complex formation in the aqueous phase should be affected to some extent by the change in the k_d value when the diluent is changed, still it may be reasonably assumed that the complex formation in the organic phase contributes the over-all rate of solvent extraction much more with the latter two β -diketones because the proportion of the reagent in the organic phase is much higher with them.

Fig. 1 gives the dependence of the rate of extraction on $[\text{H}^+]$ when the β -diketone concentration was constant. As seen from the figure, the rate of extraction is first order with respect to the β -diketone and inverse first order with respect to hydrogen ion in the lower $[\text{H}^+]$ region, but it becomes

Fig. 1. Dependence of rate of solvent extraction given by K_{obs} (cf. equation (2)) as a function of hydrogen-ion concentration when the initial β -diketone concentration in the organic phase was $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; β -diketone (○) Hbza, (●) Hbfa, and (◐) Htfa.

independent at the higher concentration range. The dependence on [HA] was also determined and the rate was found to be first order with respect to the

β -diketone concentration. Thus, equation (1) can be rewritten as

$$V = [\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HA}](k_{(0)} + k_{(-1)}[\text{H}^+]^{-1}) \quad (3)$$

From the experimental data, the value of $k_{(0)}$ and $k_{(-1)}$ were obtained as listed in Table 2(a).

In a previous study⁷, it was found that the rate of solvent extraction of iron(III) with β -diketones was inverse first order with respect to the hydrogen ion in the aqueous phase. The rate of these extractions was redetermined recently and from the new data, the rate of formation of β -diketonato complexes in the aqueous phase was calculated^{4,9}. The rate constants obtained in these previous studies are given in Table 2(b).

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF β -DIKETONES USED FOR THE DATA ANALYSIS

	Hbza	Hbfa	Htfa
log K_a^*	-9.2 ^a	-6.2 ^a	-6.6 ^b
log K_d^{**} (carbon tetrachloride)	2.7 ^a	2.5 ^a	0.4 ^b
(4-methyl-2-pentanone)	2.74	3.30	1.16

* $K_a = [\text{H}^+][\text{A}^-]/[\text{HA}]$. ** $K_d = [\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}/[\text{HA}]$ when the aqueous phase was 4 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄.
^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 6.

TABLE 2—SUMMARY OF RATE CONSTANTS

	Hbza	Hbfa	Htfa
(a) Solvent extraction in equation (3)			
log $k_{(0)}$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	-1.1	-2.6	-2.2
log $k_{(-1)}$ (s ⁻¹)	-2.5	-3.4	-2.5
(b) Complex formation in aqueous 4 mol dm ⁻³ (Na, H)ClO ₄			
log k_o^* (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	0.5 ^a	-1.4 ^a	-1.2 ^b
log k_{-1}^* (s ⁻¹)	-0.2 ^c	-1.4 ^c	-1.6 ^b
(c) Complex formation in 4-methyl-2-pentanone			
log $k_o(\text{org})^{**}$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	0.6	-1.2	—
log $k_{-1}(\text{org})^{**}$ (s ⁻¹)	-1.2	-1.7	-1.2

* $V = k_o[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HA}] + k_{-1}[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HA}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}$.
 ** $V = k_o(\text{org})[\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{ClO}_4^-)_3][\text{HA}]_{\text{org}} + k_{-1}(\text{org})[\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{ClO}_4^-)_3][\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}[\text{HClO}_4]_{\text{org}}$
^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 4. ^cRef. 7.

When the rate of extraction is controlled by both the formation of the first complex in the aqueous and in the organic phase and when the rate of extraction is equal to the over-all rate of these complex formations, the following equation may be given,

$$\begin{aligned} V &= d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{org}}/dt \\ &= k_{\text{obs}(\text{org})}[\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{ClO}_4^-)_3]_{\text{org}} \\ &\quad + k_o[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}][\text{HA}] + k_{-1}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}][\text{HA}][\text{H}^+]^{-1} \\ &= k_{\text{obs}(\text{org})}D_{\text{Fe}}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] \\ &\quad + k_o[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}][\text{HA}] + k_{-1}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}][\text{HA}][\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where, } k_{\text{obs}(\text{org})} = k_o(\text{org})[\text{HA}]_{\text{org}} + k_{-1}(\text{org})[\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}[\text{HClO}_4]_{\text{org}} \quad (5)$$

and D_{Fe} is the distribution ratio of the Fe^{III} species when the following extraction occurs⁸,

It was found that the value of D_{Fe} is to some extent dependent on the $[\text{H}^+]$ in the aqueous phase. For example, D_{Fe} between 4-methyl-2-pentanone and 4 mol dm⁻³ (Na, H)ClO₄ solution was 1.4×10^{-2} at lower acid concentration but it was 3.8×10^{-2} when the aqueous phase contained 1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and 3 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄. For this reason, the value of D_{Fe} experimentally obtained at each hydrogen ion concentration was used for the calculation.

On the basis of equations (4) and (5), the rate constants for the complex formation in the organic phase can be calculated from the experimental data as given in Fig. 2. Since the rate constants for the complex formation in the aqueous phase previously obtained are known as listed in Table 2(b), the rate of complex formation in the aqueous phase at each set of $[\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ can be calculated and by subtracting these from the rate of solvent extraction, the rate of formation of the first complex in the organic phase may be obtained.

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate of complex formation in 4-methyl-2-pentanone given by $k_{\text{obs}(\text{org})}$ (cf. equation (4)) calculated from the data in Fig. 1; β -diketone (O) Hbza, (●) Hbfa, and (◐) Htfa.

In each series of experiments in Fig. 2, the ligand concentration, $[\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}$, is approximately

identical, that is, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} . From the value of $[\text{HA}]_{\text{org}}$ and $[\text{HClO}_4]_{\text{org}}$, and those of $k_{\text{obs}(\text{org})}$ in Fig. 2, the value of $k_{0(\text{org})}$ and $k_{-1(\text{org})}$ were calculated by a curve-fitting method¹⁰. The values thus obtained are given in Table 2(c).

Much less is known about the kinetics of complex formation of iron(III) in non-aqueous solvents than in aqueous solutions^{11,12} and it seems to be difficult to consider further about the findings in the present study without information about the difference in the chemical properties of the solutes in the organic solvents and in the aqueous solutions, about the solvation and hydrolysis of the metal ions, dissociation of perchloric acid and the β -diketone, the keto-enol tautomerism, the activity of the solutes, etc. However, it can still be pointed out that the kinetic study on such an effect of the diluent should be very useful in order to make an effective solvent extraction method for inert metal ions.

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